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Dynamic symmetry in quantum-classical mechanics: Simplicity in complexity

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Introduction: As is well known, elementary transfers of electrons and/or protons in the membranes of living cells are integral parts of their functioning. Therefore, fundamental theoretical knowledge about the elementary transfers of electrons and/or protons in condensed media is of great interest. The theory of elementary transfers of electrons and/or protons in condensed media is based on a new physical theory – quantum-classical mechanics (QCM; see (1–4) and references therein). As a new theory, QCM arises as a result of eliminating the singularity that occurs in quantum mechanics (QM) in the rates of elementary electron-charge transfers when going beyond the Born-Oppenheimer adiabatic approximation and the Franck-Condon principle. This singularity can be easily demonstrated by the example of a one-dimensional potential box with a movable wall (1–4).

Methods: The singular dynamics of the joint motion of an electron and nuclei in the transient state of molecular “quantum” transitions is damping by introducing chaos into QM. This chaos arises only during molecular quantum transitions and is called dozy chaos. Dozy chaos is introduced by replacing the infinitesimal imaginary addition in the energy denominator of the full Green’s function of the electron-nuclear system with a finite value, which is called the dozy-chaos energy γ .

Results & Discussions: The result for the optical transition-rate constant does not change when the sign of γ is changed. Other dynamic symmetries appearing in theory are associated with the emergence of dynamic organization in electronic-vibrational transitions, in particular, with the emergence of an electron-nuclear-reorganization resonance (the so-called Egorov resonance) and its antisymmetric (chaotic) “twin”, with direct and reverse transitions, as well as with different values of the electron-phonon interaction in the initial and final states of the system. The efficacy of the damping for the singularity is shown by applications of the Egorov resonance to optical spectra in polymethine dyes and J-aggregates. Nonradiative transitions are considered within a simplified version of QCM (SVQCM), in which the electronic component of the complete electron-nuclear amplitude of transitions is fitted by the Gamow tunnel exponential, dependent on the transient phonon environment. Within SVQCM and the Einstein model of nuclear vibrations, the Brönsted coefficients α and β for proton-transfer reactions satisfy the well-known symmetric relation $\alpha + \beta = 1$ (5). The linearity of the Brönsted relations is explained.

Conclusions: It is proposed to generalize QCM to the case of nonlinear optics (1), which, in particular, is rationalizing experimental studies in the field of bioimaging and photodynamic therapy. Prospects for further developments in QCM and their applications to problems of cancer and viral infections are discussed.

Keywords: Charge transfer, dozy-chaos mechanics, optical band shapes, Egorov resonance, Brönsted relations

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